

Grains

Eating grains, especially whole grains, provides health benefits. People who eat grains regularly may have a reduced risk of some diseases. Grains provide many nutrients needed for the health and maintenance of our bodies.

Foods made from wheat, rice, oats, cornmeal, barley, or other grains are grain products. Examples are bread, pasta, breakfast cereals, grits, and tortillas.

Fruits

Fruits provide nutrients needed to maintain your health and body. People who eat fruits and vegetables as part of an overall diet may lower their risk of certain diseases.

The fruit group includes all fruits and 100% fruit juice. Fruits may be fresh, frozen, canned, dried or dehydrated. Eat more whole fruit.

Other helpful resources: <https://www.myplate.gov/> & <https://www.myplate.gov/myplate-kitchen/recipes>

No-Bake Energy Bites

Time: 10 minutes Servings: 30

Ingredients

- 1 cup old fashioned rolled oats
- 1/2 cup chocolate chips
- 3 Tbsp. ground flax seed (optional)
- 1/2 heaping cup peanut butter
- 4 tablespoons honey
- 1/4 teaspoon vanilla extract

Instructions

1. Combine all of the ingredients in a medium sized bowl. Mix to combine.
2. Roll into 1- 1 1/2 inch sized balls
3. Place the energy bites on a baking sheet or plate and freeze or refrigerate until fully set, about 30 minutes-1 hour
4. Place in an airtight container or ziplock bag. Store the energy bites in the fridge for 1 week, or in the freezer for up to 3 months.